

Hong Kong Education Society

Conference Program Guide

**ICBIFE 2011 ICPST 2011
ICIMCS 2011 IWFCN 2011 CADMM 2011 ICPECC 2011
ICFPSM 2011 ICLISS 2011**

December 12-13, 2011, Hong Kong

ORAC Semic

Co-sponsors

**Springer
ELSEVIER
ASME Press
Singapore Management and Sports Science Institute
Information Engineering Research Institute
Hong Kong Education Society
Society on Social Implications of Technology and Engineering
International Industrial Electronics Center**

Part I Conference Schedule

December 11, 2011, Hong Kong

10: 00-18: 00	Registration	Location: Regal Riverside Hotel, Hong Kong
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December 12, 2011, Morning, Hong Kong

Time	Activity	Location: Regal Riverside Hotel, Hong Kong
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09: 00 - 09: 15	Open Ceremony& Photo
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09: 15- 10: 00	Keynote Speech 1 <i>Prof. Patrick S.P. Wang</i>
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10: 00- 10: 15	Coffee Break
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10: 15 -11: 00	Keynote Speech 2 <i>Prof. Jun Wang</i>
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11: 00-13: 00	Oral Session 1 ICIMCS2011, ICLISS2011,CADMM2011
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12: 30-14: 00	Buffet Lunch	Location: Regal Riverside Hotel, Hong Kong
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December 12, 2011, Afternoon, Hong Kong

Time	Activity	Location: Regal Riverside Hotel, Hong Kong
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14: 00 - 18: 00	Oral Session 2 ICPESM2011, ICPST2011, IWFCN2011
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14: 00 - 18: 00	Oral Session 3 ICBIFE2011, ICPECC2011
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15: 30-15: 45	Coffee Break
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December 13, 2011, Morning, Hong Kong

Time	Activity	Location: Regal Riverside Hotel, Hong Kong
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09: 00 - 13: 00	Oral Session 4 IWFCN2011, ICPECC2011, ICPESM2011
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Oral Session 2: ICPESM2011, ICPST2011, IWFCN2011

Time: 14: 00-18: 00 December 12, 2011

The Design and Development of a Baseball Cut-Off Play Training System
Chueh-Wei Chang, Yi-Po Wu 029

A Motion Analysis System for the Baseball Pitching Using a Depth Sensor
Chueh-Wei Chang, Yi-Hao Chung, Kuei-Kang Wu 029(061)

Educational Institute Process Reengineering
Liang-Chuan Wu, Yi-Ju Su 070

The Development of Combat Sport Training Equipment
Nanthawan Aameam, Seree Tuprakay, Surawate Tocharoen 201

The body modelling through physical exercise size of the quality of life of adults
Mihăilescu Liliana, candidate Enache Carmen 219

Some Aspects of Education in Photovoltaics
Vitezslav Benda 220

Experimental Study on the Influence of Athletics Physical Exercises on the Development of the Motor Skill of Speed with Lower Secondary School
Constantin Pehoiu 251

For a New Conception on Physical Education and Sport
Constantin Pehoiu 252

Study Concerning the Kinematic Aspects of the Step from the Male Triple Jump Event
Mihai Ilie 262

Sportive Performance Optimization in Track & Field Events by the Operationalizing of the Psychic Trening
Mihăilescu Liliana, Mihăilescu Liviu 263

Comparative Study Concerning the Motivation of Practicing Athletics Exercises as Creative Activities during Leisure Time of the Gymnasium and High School Pupils
Mihăilescu Liviu, Mihăilescu Petruța 286

Using contact-less optical systems to characterize and measure deformation of TWIP materials
J. Sobotk , P. Solfronk, P. Doubek 003

Transport properties of single vanadium oxide nanowire
Kien Wen Sun 004

Analytic comparison of some epidemic models with vaccination
M. De la Sen , S. Alonso-Quesada , A. Ibeas 009

The architecture of nuclear binding energy
Russ Blake 011

The equivalence of time and gravitational field
Ilija Barukčić 020

Adsorption of Anionic, Cationic and Nonionic Surfactants on Carbonate Rock in Presence of ZrO₂ Nanoparticles
Pouriya Esmaeilzadeh, Alireza Bahramian, Zahra Fakhroueian 022

Laser technology for fabrication of silicon based surface-barrier structures
K.E. Avjyan, A.M. Khachatryan, L.A. Matevosyan, G.H. Vardanyan 030

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**2011 International Conference on Physics Science and Technology
(ICPST 2011)**

December 12-13, 2011, Hong Kong

IERI Circuit and System Society

Official Acceptance and Invited Letter

Thank you for your submission to ICPST 2011. We are pleased to inform you that your paper

Paper id: 20

Title: The equivalence of time and gravitational field

Contact Author: Ilija Barukčić

Due to review of ICPST 2011 Committees, your paper was accepted as a regular paper in ICPST 2011. Your paper will be published by Elsevier (Physics Procedia, ISSN: 1875-3892), which will be indexed by EI Compendex, ISI Proceedings (ISTP), and Scopus. Please do take into account in the revision to further improve the English quality of your paper. The regular length of the paper should not exceed 6 pages without extra pages fees.

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Registration Fees: The registration will be opened in October 15, 2011; you can download the registration form in the website and send us before October 27, 2011. Sorry for the so tight time.

We hope to see you in Hong Kong.

Program Committee of ICPST 2011
Information Engineering Research Institute, USA
2011-10-15

